

Environment and Health Securities

Research Article

Pham van Huong^{1,2*}, Bruneel JL¹, Lahaye M¹, Nguyen QH³, Chu Van Hai³

¹ University Bordeaux, Cours Liberation, Talence/Bordeaux, France.

² Elected Member of the New York Academy of Sciences, USA.

³ Centre of Analytical Services and Experimentation, Nguyen van Thu St, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Abstract

Good nutritive materials are increasing necessity not only for the population of developed countries in their more and more polluted environment but also crucial demand for population of undeveloped nations.

The author will present his research and thinking during his travels through Island, Norway, big producers of wild and elevated fishes.

Progresses in the Western and Eastern Europa are also mentioned.

Problems of defoliants in the cultivation of crops in USA, central and south-America and other countries will be revealed and solutions were suggested.

Animal nutritive from Argentina, South Asia and France, elevated in concentrated areas or affected by eating empoisoned herbicides cause less problems than the nutrition of fishes living in contact with Dioxin Orange Agent and Paraquat.

For getting better human nutritive and health securities, the author will select and suggests some solutions not only to reduce dangers but also how to the change the eating habits. In particular, restricting the industrial productions. Consumers may reduce carbohydrates and practice some physical exercises 30 minutes a day, such as progressively accelerated walking and profound respiration clean air; these could help them to get better life.

Keywords: Environment; Pollution; Health Foods; Cancer; Characterization; Solutions; Renewable and Sustainable Energies.

Introduction

Environment pollution in the present time is a very serious problem, not only for industrial countries, but also for many other areas over the world.

As modern physical analytical methods such as micro-laser-Raman spectroscopy and x-ray or electron fluorescence spectroscopy are revealed as powerful in the studies of specific high value materials [1-3], we used them for examination of pollutants in both gaseous, liquid and solid states.

Results and Discussion

Pollution of Elevated fishes in holes created by American B 52 Carpet Bombing on Viet Nam.

Some of these fishes contain omega-3 and omega-9. One friend of mine suggested to add the “smell of B52”.

The people who has eaten these fishes get evidently intestinal troubles, but more seriously for their new born children, even of the second generation.

Pollution of Fishes in Giant Farms

-The fishes elevations are much more important in the United States, Canada, Equador, India and specially in Scandinavia. Each farm owner has generally six rectangular or circular cages containing around 200.000 fishes in each. If one fish is sick, it can contaminate the sickness up to 200.000 others. To avoid it, the farmers pumped the young fishes and put them in boxes containing antibiotic and other dirty chemicals, before putting them into the cages.

*Corresponding Author:

Pham van Huong,
University Bordeaux, 351, Cours Liberation, Talence/Bordeaux, France.
Elected member of the New York Academy of Sciences, USA.
E-mail: pham.vhuong@gmail.com

Received: December 04, 2018

Accepted: November 11, 2019

Published: November 18, 2019

Citation: Pham van Huong, Bruneel JL, Lahaye M, Nguyen QH, Chu Van Hai. Environment and Health Securities. *Int J Natural Disaster Health Secur.* 2019;6(1):47-52.
doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.19070/2572-7540-190009>

Copyright: Pham van Huong[©] 2019. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Figure 1. Giant Fish Cages.

Figure 2. Small Salmon in Sweden 2018.

Figure 3. Micro-laser-Raman Spectar of Salmon Bone and a Standard Substance.

Figure 4. Micro-laser-Raman spectra of Salmon meat and a standard substance.

Figure 5. Dried Salmon Heads 2018.

As the filet of the cage let the sea water go inside, it let evidently the dirty water go out; then infect the wild fishes outside. As the later are completely free to go anywhere they want, the contamination will be extended as far as fifty miles.

The problem is crucial in Scandinavia where we have studied this

year in spot for Salmons and other big species.

The results are presented in following figures and tables (Figure 3-6).

The results showed no Pb but some elements which do not exist

Figure 6. x-ray fluorescence spectroscopy of salmon bone and meat.

in the healthy fishes. Comparison of the standard spectra allowed the identification of some standard compounds. Further studies are underway.

Salmon meat cut in slide or in fillets are destined to people of rich countries among: Americas, Europa and others. Dried salmon heads are sent to “poor” people in Benin Africa, Bangladesh and so on. Since this year, fish owners mixed the heads with the bones together and drilled them into powder before sending or mixing with other foods.

Similar effects are also obtained in the studies of other animal species such as Indian shrimps (Figure 7, 8).

The Bad Habits of Eating Cold Foods and Drinking Gaseous Beverages

In the present time, adult people, even young people have the habit to eat cold fast foods and to drink beverages containing several gazes, including also taste-increasing and sustaining substances, colorants...

Sucrose and glucose are small causes in obesity; compared to their beverages containing gazes.

These dangerous effects are rising to a so high level of obesity which I call “a new human disaster”.

Sugars

Cann and berr sugars are in the hand of very few numbers of distributors. Therefore, they impose arbitrary their conditions.

The palm sugar as well as the “thốt nốt” Vietnamese jaggery sugar have a higher taste level and a delicate fragrance. Some critics saying that plantation of palm trees causes deforestation are exaggerated and unsuitable for the present time while the dangerous synthesized aspartame, saccharine... begin to appear in trade (Figure 9).

Cây công tử stevia a natural sweetener herb, merits to be used as substance for sweetening beverages and foods.

Solutions

- We should like to suggest to the authorities to get conscience and to educate everybody especially young people in schools, families, media social groups on internet to change the consumer habits.

- Reduce the consumption of fat, meats and carbohydrates.
- Increase cooked food and fresh vegetables, salads; some aspect of the “âm-dương” (ying-yang) equilibrium.
- Physical exercises: progressively accelerate walking and cleanair-respiration .
- No necessary to boycott but make pressure on big producers and industries to moderate their advertisings and modify if possible their gazes and additives.
- Ask governmental authorities to oblige the big producers and distributors to reserve 0.5% of the income benefit to promote the above measures and help low economical people to acquire necessary non carbohydrate foods.
- I wish that the above act of conscience and solutions can help to get better life.

Wider Range of Waste Pollution

We already treated above some essential pollution problems but the subject is much wider:

- Chemical hazards in the human environment include endocrine disruptors, dioxins, other hazardous waste.
- Types of hazardous waste include ignitable, corrosive, reactive. Hazardous waste transportation, waste discharge hazards, underground storage tanks.
- Study and evaluation techniques as well as controls and treatment techniques are essential.
- The most recent laws and water quality with also discussion on the hydrologic cycle, human impact on the water cycle, hydrogeology.
- Water treatment includes chemical reactions, dosage and concentration terminology, environmental concerns, water distribution, wells, ponds, lakes, springs, or rivers.

In the course of 10 years, **U.S. aircraft sprayed over large areas**

Figure 7. Indian shrimps 2018.

Figure 8. Micro-laser-Raman spectra of Indian shrimp and standard substances.

Figure 9. Dried Stevia Leaves.

of the jungle in Vietnam nearly 20 million gallons of the Agent Orange chemical, DIOXIN, destroying crops, vegetables, plants and animals (Figure 10).

Dioxin Still Responsible for Birth Defects in Vietnam Babies
by Rishika Gupta on September 27, 2017 at 4:39 PM Environmental Health

Dioxin or Agent Orange - a Vietnam war herbicide can still be responsible for hormonal imbalances in mother and their breastfeeding children decades later, found a study conducted by Kanazawa University in Japan.

Spread of disease through the waste and by means of insects and rodents.

A new series of heartbreaking pictures has revealed **even 40 years already now, babies are still suffering horrific effects**

of Agent Orange in Vietnam.

Francis Wade captured the distressing images at the Thi Nghe and Thien Phuoc orphanages in Saigon, which are home to children defect born decades after the war.

In trying to explain the formation of cancer due to the interaction between the double helix of DNA and external agents at high concentration [4-7], PV.Huong has suggested the following mechanism (Figure 11):

Therapy includes physical and chemical processes, biological processes, different compost systems, innovative uses of general design of equipment, residue analysis and, incinerator process waste, composting and biological compost.

The disposal of solid waste includes land pollution, water pollution, air pollution [8-12].

Figure 10. Dioxin Spread.

Figure 11. Mechanism of cancerogenesis by PV.Huong.

Figure 12. Nuclear plants.

Figure 13a. Eolian plus photovoltaic panels.

Figure 13b. Concentrate solar energies

Pollution on the Neighbourhood of Nuclear Centre Power Plants

The water vapour coming from liquid water used to cool the nuclear furnace mixed with atmospheric cloud over saturation then resulted rain falls down and infects vegetables and animals as well as people who eat them (Figure 12).

Clean Equipments and Sustainable Energies Helping to the Fees of Above Actions

Some examples can be already seen with wind Eolians in Denmark, Eolian combined with solar thermodynamic panels, and concentrated solar energies by means of parabolic furnaces in Spain and USA (Figure 13).

The Figures 10, 12, 13 came from internet.

Emergencies

I also suggest to responsible authorities to take care before too late of:

- Terrorism
- Environmental Health Emergencies
- The nature of terrorism, various acts including *biological, chemical, nuclear, radiological, electrical systems, agricultural, cyber pollutions.*
- Strategic Plan Response and Combating.
- Centers for Diseases.
- Best deal with *earthquakes, floods, forest fires, hurricanes, landslides, radiological spills, tornadoes, windstorm, and tsunami.*

-The disasters at Chernobyl and Fukushima are two events enough significant to give us precious lessons.

References

- [1]. Huong PV, Verma AL. Presence of tri-iodide ions in iodine-intercalated superconductors. *Phys Rev B Condens Matter.* 1993 Oct 1;48(13):9869-9872. PubMed PMID: 10007246.
- [2]. Huong PV, Ajayan PM, Cavagnat R, Stephan O. Temperature-dependent vibrational spectra of carbon nanotubes. *Phys Rev B Condens Matter.* 1995 Apr 15;51(15):10048-10051. PubMed PMID: 9977680.
- [3]. Choy JH, Kim YI, Hwang SJ, Muraoka Y, Ohnishi N, P.V.Huong, et al. HRTEM and Micro-Raman Studies on Superconducting- Superionic Conducting Nanohybrid, Ag₁. 1711. 54Bi2Sr2CaCu2O_y, *J Phys Chem B.* 2000 Oct 5;104(39):9086-9090.
- [4]. Huong PV. Metallo-organic complexes and carcinogenesis. In *Molecules in Physics, Chemistry, and Biology* 1989 (pp. 87-108). Springer, Dordrecht.
- [5]. Plouvier SR, Huong P, Lambert P. Bacterial chromosphere and Metals in Cancer, Leukemias and Chronic Diseases. A study by Scanning Electron Microscopy, laser Raman and Electron Micro spectroscopies. 4th Eur. Cce on Clinical Haemorheology, Siena. 1985 Jan 1; 5(5):624-624.
- [6]. Huong PV. Organometallic interactions in biological systems. *Journal of Molecular Structure.* 1986 Mar;141:203-9.
- [7]. Huong P. Raman Spectroscopy for Biological Applications in Analytical Raman Spectroscopy. Wiley, New York. 1989. 114: 397-423.
- [8]. Koren H, Bisesi MS. Biological, chemical, and physical agents of environmentally related disease. 4th ed. *Handbook of environmental health, volume I.* CRC press; 2002 Jul 29. p. 824.
- [9]. Rishika Gupta, Dioxin or Agent orange - A Vietnam war herbicide, *Environmental Health* (2017).
- [10]. van Huong P. Climate Change through the Studies of Volcano Rocks and Blue Icebergs. *Int J Natural Disaster Health Secur.* 2015 Oct 7;2(1):1-5.
- [11]. Pham v Huong , V T Kim Ngoc, Vu Hung Thai, Thanh le T, PhanThHai. Study of Colorectal Cancer by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance. *Intl J Mag Nucl Sci.* 2015 December 07; 1(1): 1-5.
- [12]. Pham van Huong, Huynh ThanhDat, Nguyen Quoc Hung (2017) Environmental Pollution, Causes and Consequences. *Intl J Natural Disaster Health Secur.* 2017 February 14; 4(1), 17-21.